

Evaluation of Rohypnol-Induced Acute Neurotoxicity in Male Wistar Rats

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Abstract

Rohypnol (Flunitrazepam), a benzodiazepine, is commonly used as a pre-anesthetic and for insomnia treatment. However, it is also frequently abused for its sedative and amnestic effects, raising concerns regarding its neurotoxic potential. This study aimed to evaluate the acute neurotoxic effects of Rohypnol on cognitive function, cholinergic activity, and oxidative stress in the brains of male Wistar rats. Twenty male Wistar rats (180–200 g) were divided into two groups: control (Group A) and Rohypnol-treated (Group B). Rohypnol was administered at a dose of 0.1 mg/kg orally for 7 days. Behavioral testing included the T-maze to assess spatial memory, the Y-maze for spontaneous alternation, and the Light-Dark box test for anxiety-like behavior. Biochemical assays were performed to measure acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity, and oxidative stress markers, including malondialdehyde (MDA) levels, superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione peroxidase (GST), glutathione (GSH), and catalase activity in brain homogenates. Rats treated with Rohypnol showed a significant reduction in spontaneous alternation in the Y-maze, suggesting impairments in spatial memory ($p < 0.05$). Rohypnol-exposed rats also spent significantly more time in the dark compartment of the Light-Dark box test, indicating increased anxiety-like behavior ($p < 0.05$). Biochemically, Rohypnol administration led to a significant increase in AChE activity and MDA levels, indicating disrupted cholinergic signaling and neuronal oxidative damage ($p < 0.05$). Additionally, oxidative stress markers including SOD, GSH, GST, and catalase were significantly elevated in the brains of Rohypnol-treated rats ($p < 0.05$), suggesting a compensatory response to oxidative damage. Acute exposure to Rohypnol induces significant neurotoxic effects in male Wistar rats, as evidenced by impaired cognitive performance, increased anxiety-like behavior, and biochemical markers of oxidative stress and cholinergic dysfunction. These findings highlight the potential neurotoxic effects of Rohypnol, particularly in cases of misuse or overdose, and underscore the need for further research on its long-term impact on brain function and health.

More Information

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Introduction

Drug misuse is a worldwide issue, and it can lead to socio-medical issues. Among the most often misused substances in many countries, including Nigeria, are benzodiazepines, cocaine, cannabis, opioids, and amphetamines [1,2]. A potent hypnotic and pre-anaesthetic medication [3], rohypnol is used to treat short-term insomnia [4]. By raising γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA) activity, rohypnol can cause hyperactivity and violence [5]. Additionally, it has been connected to organ damage, poor mental health, and even death [6,7]. Rohypnol can also be utilized as a skeletal-muscle relaxant and to treat epileptic disorders [8]. Leo Sternbach's benzodiazepine research at Roche resulted to its discovery; the patent application was submitted in 1962, and it was first put on the market in 1974 [9]. Rohypnol is a pill that is often marketed in the bubble packaging provided by the manufacturer. It is made by fluorinating the N-methyl derivative of the benzodiazepine class hypnotic nitrazepam [10].

Rohypnol is a depressant of the central nervous system [11]. The brain and the spinal cord that extends from it make up the central nervous system [12]. All body processes, including thought, emotion, motor skills, vision, metabolism, and appetite, are controlled by the brain, a complex organ. Abuse of rohypnol causes long-term brain damage and can have detrimental effects, such as diminished motor abilities and significant memory loss [13, 14]. By attaching to receptors on brain neurons that use the neurotransmitter gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), benzodiazepines change behavior. GABA naturally lowers anxiety and controls brain activity. It attaches itself to receptors, suppressing neurons and reducing their activity [5]. Benzodiazepines increase GABA's interaction with receptors by binding to them. This increases GABA's effects while lowering brain activity, which results in drowsiness or relaxation. GABA is also in charge of regulating dopamine levels. A benzodiazepine study claims that drugs like Rohypnol reduce the inhibition of dopamine production by impairing GABA receptor activity [15]. Young people are using rohypnol more and more, and it is abused in many social contexts, including in nations where it is prohibited [4]. There have been some instances linking the medical use of benzodiazepines to misuse. Rohypnol may cause pharmacological side effects like drowsiness, memory loss, and behavioural disinhibition, which is the term used to describe an increase in the likelihood of behaviours that are uncommon because of interpersonal, social, and cultural constraints, like violence and inappropriate sexual behaviour. Increased risk behaviour, aggressiveness, and risky sexual activity in patients linked to Rohypnol consumption may be explained by these forgetful and disinhibitory effects

[4]. Despite the ubiquity of Rohypnol abuse and its potential damage to organs, including neuronal impairment, research on the effects of Rohypnol exposure on brain tissue is limited. Rohypnol's impact on brain integrity and redox status is assessed in this study. The functions of the cholinesterase enzyme activities and glutathione system, as well as the behavioural pattern in Rohypnol-induced alteration in the brain of male Wistar rats, were examined because they work in concert to protect cells through oxidative-sensitive signalling, which has been connected to a number of tissue/organ damage [16,17].

Materials and Methods

Materials

Rohypnol (Flunitrazepam 90 mg) was purchased from AZ Pharmacy, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. To homogenize the pills, a laboratory-grade mortar and pestle were used until a smooth powdery consistency was obtained [51]. The rohypnol powder was dissolved in distilled water obtained from Lead City University biochemistry laboratory, Ibadan, Nigeria to form a homogenous mixture for administration to the rats. The compound was manufactured by Hoffmann-La Roche (Basel, Switzerland), with a certified purity of ≥ 98 . All handling, storage, and experimental preparations were conducted in accordance with the manufacturer's guidelines to ensure the integrity and stability of the compound throughout the study. All chemicals, the AchE, SOD, GST, GSH assay kits and thiobarbituric acid were obtained from Sigma (St Louis, Missouri) and prepared and used according to the instructions of the manufacturer for assay accuracy and consistency.

Material and Methods

Experimental Animals

Twenty (20) adult male Wistar rats (180 - 200g) were purchased from the animal breeding section at the University of Ibadan, Nigeria, and housed in Lead City University, Nigeria, Animal House in well-aerated cages at a temperature ranging between 25-27°C and humidity levels of 50-55% on a 12-hour light/dark cycle. Water and standard animal diet were given ad libitum for 14 days before the start of this research.

Animal Grouping and Treatment

Following acclimatization, the animals were randomly assigned to two (2) groups of ten animals each (n=10).

- Group A (Control) was given 0.1 ml of distilled water only via the oral route.
- Group B (Rohypnol) was exposed to 0.1 mg/kg of Rohypnol orally for 7 days. (Acute exposure).

Behavioural Tests

The behavioural tests were performed in a big, quiet room between 9 a.m. and 5 p.m. The T-maze and Y-maze were used to test cognition, spontaneous alternation, and locomotor activity, while the Light-

dark box was used to investigate the anxiolytic effects of Rohypnol. The investigations were carried out on independent rats in each experimental setup, with all rats in one group tested on the same day. Behavioral assessments were conducted in a fixed sequence to minimize stress, learning, and carry-over effects. The rats were evaluated in the following order: T-maze, Y-maze, and the Light-dark box test.

An interval of at least 24 hours was provided between successive tests to allow adequate recovery and to avoid fatigue or task-induced sensitization. All behavioural sessions were recorded and analyzed using the EthoVision XT 15. The software was used to automatically track locomotion, exploration, and anxiety-related parameters, ensuring objective and standardized data acquisition. To prevent observer bias, all video files were coded, and the observers performing the scoring were blinded to the treatment groups throughout the analysis. Apparatuses were thoroughly cleaned with 70% ethanol and allowed to air-dry between trials to eliminate residual scents and prevent behavioural cues from previously tested animals. These procedures ensured that the recorded behavioural outcomes accurately reflected each animal's true performance, free from confounding influences such as stress, learning carry-over, environmental contamination, or observer bias.

T-Maze tests

The T-maze test was carried out according to the method of d'Isa [18] to assess animal cognition and spontaneous alternation. The T-maze is a T-shaped apparatus with a stem (the starting arm) and two transverse goal arms. The approach is based on rats' inherent preference for exploring a novel arm over a known one, which causes them to switch between the choice of the goal arm over multiple trials.

Y-Maze Test

The Y-maze test was carried out according to the procedure established by Kraeuter et al. [19] to assess short-term memory, general locomotor activity, and stereotypic behaviour in rats exposed to Rohypnol. Spontaneous alternation, an assessment of spatial working memory, can be evaluated by allowing animals to explore all three arms of the maze, which is motivated by rats' natural urge to explore previously unexplored locations. An animal with intact working memory, and thus intact prefrontal cortex functioning, will recall previously visited arms and prefer to enter a less recently visited arm [52].

Light-dark box Test

The Light-dark box test was conducted based on the protocol described by Kuleskaya and Voikar [20]. It is a standard test for detecting anxiety-like behaviour in laboratory animals. It depends on quantifying the animals' innate aversion to highly illuminated and open

regions and spontaneous novelty-induced exploratory behaviour.

Preparation of Brain Homogenate

Following the behavioural evaluations, the rats were anaesthetized with an N-hexane gas medium and sacrificed via cervical dislocation. The brains were excised and cleansed of any adherent connective tissues. Each rat's brain was weighed and homogenised (REMI Homogenizer, Mumbai, India) with 50 mM Tris-HCl buffer (0.1 M, pH 7.4). Then, brain tissue homogenates were centrifuged (Thermo Scientific Sorvall ST 16R, Fremont, California) at 5000 rpm for 10 minutes at 4 °C. The supernatants were subsequently divided into distinct aliquots and stored at -20°C for biochemical tests, and the pellets were discarded. All biochemical assays were performed in triplicate, and each sample was analyzed in three independent runs to ensure accuracy, reproducibility, and reliability of the results.

Acetylcholinesterase Activity Assay

The brain acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity was assayed in the homogenate collected and measured at a wavelength of 412 nm according to the modified procedure of Ellman [21] and expressed as $\mu\text{mol}/\text{substrate hydrolysed}/\text{min}/\text{mg protein}$.

Biological Antioxidant Assays

Catalase activity was determined in brain homogenate using hydrogen peroxide as a substrate, at a wavelength of 240 nm, as described by Claiborne et al. [22]. Superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity was evaluated at 525 nm according to the method of Misra and Fridovich [23,53]. Glutathione-S-transferase (GST) activity was measured in the brain homogenate using 1-chloro-2, 4-dinitrobenzene as the substrate, at 345 nm following the procedure of Habig et al. [24,53]. Reduced glutathione (GSH) was evaluated at 415 nm using the method reported by Beutler et al. [25]. Lipid peroxidation was measured as malondialdehyde (MDA) using the Varshney and Kale method at a wavelength of 532nm [26] and expressed in $\text{nmol}/\text{mg protein}$. The total protein concentration was measured using the biuret method [27].

Statistical Analysis

Data were analysed using SPSS version 20 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA) and presented as mean \pm SEM (standard mean error). Duncan's multiple range tests were used to establish the level of significance between the treatment means with a p-value of less than 0.05.

Results

Effect of Rohypnol on T-maze Spatial Memory

Figure A shows the impact of Rohypnol (0.1 mg/kg) on spatial memory as assessed by the T-maze test. After 5 minutes of exposure, rats treated with Rohypnol exhibited a trend toward lower spatial memory performance compared to the control group. However,

the difference between groups was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Effect of Rohypnol on Spontaneous alternation (Y-Maze)

In the Y-maze spontaneous alternation test (Figure b), Rohypnol-treated rats exhibited a significant reduction in spontaneous alternation compared to the control group ($p < 0.05$).

Effect of Rohypnol on Anxiety (Light and Dark box test)

Results from the Light and Dark Box Test (Figure c) indicate that Rohypnol-treated rats spent significantly less time in the light compartment compared to the control group ($p < 0.05$), while they spent more time in the dark compartment [54].

Figure 1: Results of the Behavioural investigations. a) Effect of Rohypnol (0.1 mg/kg) on rats' T-maze spatial memory after 5 minutes of exploration. b) Effect of Rohypnol on spontaneous alternation (Y-maze). c) Effect of Rohypnol on rats to assess anxiety (Light and Dark box test)

Note: Data are presented as mean \pm SEM (n=10), $p < 0.05$. Statistical analysis was performed using a one-way ANOVA, and significant differences between groups were identified using Duncan's multiple range test.

Source: [54]

Effect of Rohypnol Administration on Acetylcholinesterase Activity in the Brain

Figure 2 presents the effect of Rohypnol exposure on acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity in the brains of male Wistar rats after 7 days of treatment. Post-hoc analysis revealed a significant increase in AChE activity in the Rohypnol-treated rats compared to controls ($p < 0.05$).

Effect of Rohypnol Administration on MDA Level in the Brain of Male Wistar Rat.

As shown in Figure 3, MDA levels, a marker of lipid peroxidation and cellular membrane damage, were significantly higher in the brains of Rohypnol-treated rats compared to controls ($p < 0.05$).

Effect of Rohypnol Exposure on Neuro-Oxidative Stress Biomarkers (SOD GSH, GST and Catalase)

The enzymatic antioxidant proteins in the Rohypnol-exposed rat brain post mitochondrial homogenates are presented in Figures 4 through 7. The results depict a considerable increase ($p < 0.05$) in SOD, GSH, GST and catalase in animals intoxicated with Rohypnol (0.1

mg/kg) for 7 days in relation to the corresponding control [53].

Figure 2: Effect of Rohypnol on brain acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity after 7 days of exposure

Note: Data are presented as mean+SEM (n=10), $p < 0.05$. Statistical analysis was performed using a one-way ANOVA, and significant differences between groups were identified using Duncan's multiple range test

Source: [54]

Figure 3: Effect of MDA on brain malonaldehyde (MDA) level in animals exposed to Rohypnol for 7 days

Note: Data are presented as mean+SEM (n=10), p < 0.05. Statistical analysis was performed using a one-way ANOVA, and significant differences between groups were identified using Duncan's multiple range test

Source: [54]

Figure 6: Effect of Rohypnol administration on Brain reduced glutathione (GSH) activity in animals

Note: Data are presented as mean+SEM (n=10), p < 0.05. Statistical analysis was performed using a one-way ANOVA, and significant differences between groups were identified using Duncan's multiple range test

Source: [54]

Figure 4: Effect of Rohypnol on brain superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity following 7 day of administration

Note: Data are presented as mean+SEM (n=10), p < 0.05. Statistical analysis was performed using a one-way ANOVA, and significant differences between groups were identified using Duncan's multiple range test

Source: [54]

Figure 7: Effect of Rohypnol (0.1 mg/kg) administration on Brain catalase activity in rats

Note: Data are presented as mean+SEM (n=10), p < 0.05. Statistical analysis was performed using a one-way ANOVA, and significant differences between groups were identified using Duncan's multiple range test

Source: [54]

Figure 5: Effect of Rohypnol administration on Brain glutathione S-transferase (GST) activity in animals

Note: Data are presented as mean+SEM (n=10), p < 0.05. Statistical analysis was performed using a one-way ANOVA, and significant differences between groups were identified using Duncan's multiple range test

Source: [54].

Discussion

As a result of growing misuse, rohypnol poisoning has emerged as a serious worldwide concern. It is a risk factor for organ damage due to its high exposure rate and toxic consequences, just as the majority of drugs of abuse. Therefore, protecting the health of people who have been exposed and those who are at risk requires an understanding of the consequences and related mechanisms of Rohypnol exposure [28]. Memory loss, difficulty moving, unconsciousness, and behavioural disinhibition are among the pharmacological side effects of rohypnol [29].

One sign of brain injury is disinhibition [30]. Generalized cognitive impairment, with more obvious irregularities in the rate of information processing, attentiveness, memory, and cognitive flexibility, may be one of the neuropsychiatric effects of brain injury [31]. Benzodiazepines and other central nervous system

depressants have been linked to behavioral disinhibition as a result of neurological damage [32].

We investigated the acute neurotoxic effects of Rohypnol on cognitive function, cholinergic and antioxidant enzyme activity in the brains of experimental rats. The study found that Rohypnol-treated rats exhibit avoidance behaviour, as shown by a substantial attraction for the dark compartment over the light compartment when compared to the untreated rats. Furthermore, the administration of Rohypnol results in a considerable increase in open-arm avoidance in the T and Y mazes compared to the control, indicating anxiogenic-like traits. The frequency of closed-arm entries also serves as an indicator of locomotor activity.

Our findings revealed an increase in the number of closed-arm entries. Furthermore, in the Y-maze, rats exposed to Rohypnol showed a decline in spontaneous alternation compared to the control group, indicating spatial memory impairment. Prior studies on brain injury have discovered strong connections between disinhibition syndromes and orbitofrontal and basotemporal cortical abnormalities, which impact intellectual capacity, spatial memory, and visuospatial functions [30]. Some authors have reported that Rohypnol alters short-term working and reference memory [33] and is detrimental to coordination [34]. Neuronal toxicity resulted from the disruption of the brain's Rohypnol-neurotransmitter GABA (gamma-aminobutyric acid) balance induced by an increase in neuronal Rohypnol levels following acute oral Rohypnol ingestion.

Acetylcholine (ACh), a cholinergic neurotransmitter, is crucial for memory and learning [35]. Acetylcholinesterase is the main enzyme that deactivates ACh in the synaptic gap, its activity is a well-known marker of cholinergic neuron injury in the brain [36]. Since AChE is a crucial neurotransmitter signaling molecule involved in neurogenesis, we looked into how Rohypnol affected its activity [37]. Rohypnol significantly increased AChE activity in the rats' brains, according to the data from our investigation.

These results implied that there was a damage to the brain cells' dopaminergic and cholinergic circuits. According to earlier studies, those who abuse Rohypnol may have abnormal cholinergic/dopaminergic balance in their brains due to elevated GABA [15]. GABA typically restricts a neuron's ability to communicate with its neighbors. The effects of GABA are enhanced by elevated neuronal Rohypnol levels, which further inhibit neuronal transmission. The depressed impact, another name for this reduced communication, causes fatigue and disorientation, which might eventually result in a coma or even death. The observation that diazepam inhibits AChE activity in the rat cerebral

cortex is in conflict with the apparent increase of AChE activity by Rohypnol [38].

A sign of oxidative stress, lipid peroxidation is the oxidative degradation of membrane lipids that damages cells [39]. This investigation demonstrated that Rohypnol significantly ($p < 0.05$) raised the brain's malondialdehyde level when compared to the control group. This is consistent with the findings of Kapur and Katarina [40], who observed that Rohypnol can induce lipid peroxidation. Reactive oxygen species overproduction that surpasses the antioxidant system's buffering ability is known as oxidative stress [17]. GSH is an inherent antioxidant that plays important roles in neurotransmission and other central nervous system processes [41].

The glutathione system, which is formed by GSH and a variety of enzymes, is necessary to regulate reactive oxygen species (ROS) and nitrogen species (RNS) in living things. By regulating cell metabolism and maintaining cellular redox homeostasis, the glutathione redox cycle preserves the body's cellular antioxidant defence [42]. It is commonly known that the glutathione system and oxidative stress play a role in drug-induced organ damage [17,43]. Rohypnol-induced increase in neuronal GSH, GST, catalase and SOD activities in this study are suggestive of Rohypnol-induced oxidative stress in the brain of the rats. Oxidative damage has been linked to Rohypnol treatment in animal models and humans [7].

The increased MDA in the brain may be a consequence of an integrated effort of the accumulation of reactive oxygen species, triggering dysfunctional GSH, and the excessive generation of free radicals during acute Rohypnol exposure, leading to neuronal toxicity [28, 44]. These findings align with previous studies on the production of oxidative harm by drugs of abuse such as codeine [45] and tramadol [46]. It is plausible to conclude that Rohypnol increased brain antioxidant enzymes, leading to redox dysregulation and oxidative stress.

Consistent with recent studies [43, 47, 48], acute exposure to Rohypnol for 7 days in our investigation resulted in an increase in GST and modifications of the neuronal antioxidant pool, specifically SOD and catalase. The rise in GST status, along with associated alterations in SOD and catalase activities, further explains the mechanism of neuronal toxicity triggered by acute neuronal Rohypnol exposure and could be due to the production of free radicals, which has been demonstrated to have detrimental impacts on cells, tissues, and organs [42, 49, 53]. The elevated MDA level suggests oxidative damage to membrane lipids, resulting in oxidative injury within the affected tissues. It is also noted that Endocrine-disrupting chemicals (EDCs) are widespread environmental pollutants that

disrupt hormonal control and lead to reproductive, developmental, and metabolic issues [50]

In response to the increased oxidative burden, the antioxidant defense system appeared to activate a compensatory adaptive response. This was demonstrated by the significant elevation in the activities of key antioxidant enzymes, including superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), glutathione (GSH), and glutathione S-transferase (GST). The upregulation of these antioxidant enzymes activities is a characteristic cellular mechanism aimed at neutralizing the reactive oxygen species and restoring redox balance. The simultaneous rise in both antioxidant enzymes and MDA suggests that although the antioxidant machinery is activated, it may not be sufficiently effective to fully prevent oxidative injury. Persistent reactive oxygen species production could eventually overwhelm these defenses, leading to progressive cellular and tissue damage.

Conclusion

Rohypnol (0.1 mg/kg) caused neuronal deficits in rats after treatment, and this could be seen in the form of oxidative damage and elevated glutathione antioxidant system activity. The rats' brain behavior also changed, and this is suggestive of memory retardant effect and a major anxiogenic effect. The study showed that Rohypnol considerably reduces cognitive abilities and causes anxiety-like behaviors in male Wistar rats, even at a modest dosage of 0.1 mg/kg. Rise in antioxidant enzymes (catalase, GST, GSH, and SOD) points to a compensatory reaction to oxidative damage brought on by the medication.

The study also recorded increase in brain acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity suggests a possible disturbance of the cholinergic system, which might be the cause of cognitive impairments that were seen in the research. The results point to a connection between neurobehavioral impairment and oxidative stress brought on by Rohypnol. The study emphasizes how hazardous Rohypnol may be, even at low dosages, and how crucial it is to conduct more research on the drug's long-term effects on behavior and brain function.

Ethics Approval

The research work titled "*Evaluation of Rohypnol-Induced Acute Neurotoxicity in Male Wistar Rats*" was carried out at Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria and was granted ethical approval by Oyo State Ministry of Health Research Ethics Committee (HREC) with NREC Assigned number: NHREC/OYOSHRIEC/10/11/22. All experimental procedures involving animals in this study were conducted in accordance with the guidelines for the care and use of laboratory animals as outlined by the National Institutes of Health (NIH) Guide for the care and use of laboratory animals. Efforts were made to minimize the number of animals used and to alleviate any pain or distress.

This Study is not a Clinical Trial Consent to publish declaration

Not applicable.

Consent to Participate

Not applicable.

Availability of Data and Materials

The datasets during and/or analysed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request. All data generated or analysed during this study are included in this manuscript.

Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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